

SoK: Security of the Image Processing Pipeline for Camera-based Sensing in Autonomous Vehicles

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Abstract

Cameras are crucial sensors for autonomous vehicles. They capture images that are essential for many safety-critical tasks. To process these images, a complex pipeline with multiple layers is used. Security attacks on this pipeline can severely affect passenger safety and system performance. However, many attacks presented in scientific literature overlook the fact that there are different layers and, hence, the feasibility and impact of these attacks can vary. While there has been research to improve the quality and robustness of the image processing pipeline, these efforts are often orthogonal to security research without exploiting potential overlap and synergies. In this work, we aim to bridge this gap by combining security and robustness research for the image processing pipeline in autonomous vehicles. We thoroughly investigated the body of literature on the security and robustness of the image processing pipeline and selected 92 papers for deeper discussion in this SoK. For the security domain, we classify the risk of attacks using the automotive security standard ISO 21434, emphasizing the need to consider all layers for overall system security. With our online tool TARA-CAM, we propose an interactive method to perform threat analysis and risk assessment following the ISO standard. We also demonstrate how existing robustness research can help mitigate the impact of attacks, addressing the current research gap. Finally, we present PICT, an embedded open-source testbed that can influence various parameters across all layers, allowing researchers to analyze the effects of different defense strategies and attack impacts. With this SoK, we contribute a comprehensive discussion and systematic analysis of existing approaches to image processing pipeline security and robustness, together with an open-source tool and testbed that jointly facilitates hardening the image processing pipeline against existing and future security attacks.

CCS Concepts

• Security and privacy → Systems security; • Computing methodologies → Image and video acquisition.

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Figure 1: Abstraction of the image processing pipeline of autonomous vehicles and the main contribution of our SoK.

Keywords

Autonomous Vehicles, Cameras, Security, Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment

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1 Introduction

Autonomous vehicles and emerging advanced driver assistance systems have become a reality in recent years [85, 139]. These vehicles depend on sensing systems to interpret their surroundings and make real-time decisions. Many autonomous vehicles integrate LiDAR or radar, but camera systems are widely used as single information source for tasks such as traffic sign detection, traffic light recognition, and lane detection [40, 55] due to their ability to capture color information of the environment. Attacks on other sensors and sensor fusion have been examined in prior research [17, 116, 119], but these do not replace the need for a detailed study of camera pipelines. Because cameras are often a primary or sole perception sensor, securing their image processing pipeline is critical, both for camera-only platforms and for multi-sensor systems where compromised visual input can still mislead fused perception. The high

information density and environmental exposure of cameras enlarge the attack surface [15, 33, 40, 74, 102, 152], posing severe risks, especially in fully autonomous vehicles without human fallback. Camera-based systems face diverse attacks that exploit both hardware and algorithmic weaknesses, including adversarial physical perturbations that mislead object detection [4, 45, 134, 136, 140, 141], blinding attacks using directed light [100, 137], and exploits targeting sensor-specific characteristics [68, 71, 117]. These threats have been shown to be particularly effective against Machine Learning (ML) algorithms [127] that are often used in autonomous vehicles, and their effectiveness often depends on how they interact with different stages of the image processing pipeline. Analyzing and systematizing security and robustness research across this pipeline is the focus of our work.

Image capturing is not a simple, monolithic process but rather involves a complex, multi-stage pipeline. Figure 2 illustrates this complexity, showing how data flows from the physical world to Computer Vision (CV) algorithms in the application layer (details on the pipeline are given in §2). Ensuring the security of the image processing pipeline requires a deep understanding of its operational principles and a thorough identification of potential attack vectors. Our Systematization of Knowledge (SoK) reveals a significant gap in the current research landscape: While well-known existing work focuses narrowly on the application layer, such as by modifying ML model inputs [4, 156], or on real-world scenarios, such as crafting adversarial patterns or objects [34, 45, 141], they *overlook the impact of different layers of the image processing pipeline on the attack*.

Many attacks rely on *varied threat models and assumptions, often neglecting the significance of the entire image processing pipeline*. This oversight leads to inconsistent and misleading risk assessments. For example, our systematic analysis indicates that application layer attacks require more sophisticated capabilities than those aiming at the physical world when considering the complete pipeline. This significantly impacts the feasibility of attacks and, consequently, their associated risks. Without a common threat analysis and risk assessment, *we risk making unrealistic evaluations of certain attacks*. To address this issue, our SoK systematically analyzes and classifies security-related studies, adapting the ISO 21434 standard [56], intending to establish a consistent and comprehensive threat model that accurately evaluates risks across the entire pipeline.

While many attacks on the image processing pipeline exist, defensive research is significantly underrepresented. By contrast, many studies in the robustness domain have been more comprehensive and have considered the complex image processing pipeline. However, these studies primarily focus on mitigating environmental influences and improving performance benchmarks [13] rather than addressing intentionally crafted attacks. As a result, *works from the robustness domain are not sufficiently considered to secure the image processing pipeline*. Our SoK aims to bridge this critical gap by integrating insights from both security and robustness domains. By doing so, we seek to help researchers develop a more resilient system that combines the strengths of works from both domains.

Finally, the complexity of image processing pipelines and their extensive configuration options reveal another significant gap: *no existing testbed in the scientific community effectively addresses the full spectrum of pipeline layers and configurations*. Existing studies often rely on simulations [14, 15] or use unrealistic hardware (e.g.,

smartphones [17] or semi-professional cameras [154]). Furthermore, prior hardware testbeds [1, 112] lack full pipeline coverage and up-to-date technology. Our paper addresses this gap by proposing PICT (PICT is an Image Capture Testbed), a new testbed that integrates carefully selected hardware that mimics contemporary automotive systems, covers all pipeline layers, is cost-effective, open-source, and easy to reproduce. PICT provides insights into both the security and robustness of the image processing pipeline and facilitates testing attacks and countermeasures.

We make the following contributions as shown in Figure 1:

- **Systematizing security and robustness research.** We provide a comprehensive analysis of 92 papers – 56 on security and 36 on robustness. For each domain, we *classify* and *contextualize* the existing work, assess its impact, and identify key observations (§3 and §5).
- **Evaluating risk and threat models of existing attacks.** To guide future research and enable focused investigation of critical threats, we systematically *analyze* and *classify* security-related research using the ISO 21434 standard (§4). We also release the open-source tool TARA-CAM¹, enabling replication of our analysis and consistent evaluation of similar attacks, thereby offering a more consistent approach to threat assessment.
- **Bridging security and robustness research.** Based on the analysis of research papers from both security and robustness domains, we establish links to increase awareness across the domains for more integrated future research (§6).
- **Introducing PICT, a testbed for the image processing pipeline.** We developed an open-source² testbed, PICT, deployed on embedded hardware to address the current gap in evaluating image processing pipelines. PICT integrates carefully selected hardware and covers all pipeline layers. It aims to enhance the understanding of attack impact and the effectiveness of countermeasures on image processing pipelines. To demonstrate its usability, we use the tool to showcase representative attacks and the effectiveness of defense mechanisms (§7 and §8).

2 Image Processing Pipeline

Figure 2 illustrates a manufacturer-agnostic image processing pipeline, which consists of four main layers: physical world, sensor layer, data preparation layer, and application layer. Data captured from the physical world moves from the sensor layer via the data preparation layer to the application layer. Additionally, control signals from software components on the application layer can influence the data preparation layer and the sensor layer. It is important to note that we use these layers conceptually; thus, the mapping of these layers to actual hardware platforms may vary. For example, components of the data preparation layer and the application layer can run on the same physical device [62, 66]. Similarly, the application layer may be integrated into different hardware components. While real-world automotive image processing pipelines include

¹<https://tum-esi.github.io/PICT/>

²<https://github.com/tum-esi/PICT>

Figure 2: Overview of the image processing pipeline, consisting of four layers. Hardware components like the image sensor have solid edges, while software-configurable components have rounded corners, such as the Image Signal Processor.

manufacturer-specific constraints and parameters, they share common functional stages, enabling manufacturer-agnostic analysis.

Physical World: The physical world represents all visible objects in the field of view, such as street signs, road markings, pedestrians, and road users. Since an image sensor is sensitive to photons, it will capture all entities, such as objects or displayed content, emitting or reflecting photons. The more photons an entity emits or passively reflects, the higher the captured and digitized value will be at a dedicated position. Therefore, other influences in the physical world, like sunbeams, shadows, or weather [18], can significantly impact the subsequent layers of the image processing pipeline.

Sensor Layer: It is the first layer that senses and processes the photons emitted by the physical world. It is important to differentiate between the terms *camera* and *image sensor*. While every camera includes an image sensor, it typically comprises additional optical and electrical components, as shown in Figure 2. Within this layer, photons are directed through one or more lenses [37]. These lenses can either be fixed in position, providing a fixed focus, or be adjustable, allowing dynamic focus control [106]. Once the light passes through the lenses, it reaches the image sensor.

This sensing element can be a Charge-coupled device (CCD) or Complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) array composed of usually multiple millions of photosensitive elements. Since these photosensitive elements cannot differentiate colors, a color filter array (CFA) is placed on top of the sensing array [32]. Various CFAs are available for different use cases [106], with the Bayer pattern being the most prominent CFA [37]. A Bayer pattern consists of a 2×2 pixel matrix, with one red, two green, and one blue pixel (also called RGGB). Especially in the automotive industry, different variations of this original Bayer pattern exist, such as RCCC or RCCB, where "C" stands for "clear" pixels, meaning that they are not sensitive to only a specific color [142]. Figure 2 shows different CFAs which are common in research and industry.

After sensing light via CCD or CMOS technology, a readout circuit converts the analog measured values into digital ones for further processing [160]. For CMOS sensors, this readout circuit often operates in a *rolling-shutter* mode, where the entire pixel array is read out line by line [117] in contrast to CCD sensors [68]. Once digital values are available, many manufacturer-specific on-chip processing steps are performed [14, 18]. These operations can

include defect pixel correction, image cropping, tone mapping, and simple denoising [106]. In the automotive industry, High Dynamic Range (HDR) image sensors are often used, with a higher dynamic range than typical sensors. This is achieved either by combining multiple photosensitive elements per pixel [143] or by merging images of the same scene captured with different settings [50, 84]. Finally, the partially processed digital image is serialized into a data stream for electronic transmission. A typical interface for this purpose is the Camera Serial Interface 2 (CSI-2) by the MIPI Alliance [86]. For data transmission over longer distances, the CSI-2 protocol is often serialized using proprietary standards [129].

Data Preparation Layer: The first operation within this layer involves deserializing the received data and delivering it to an Image Signal Processor (ISP) for further processing. The primary goal of an ISP is to optimally prepare the captured image for subsequent use, such as displaying it for the human eye [106] or preparing it for CV algorithms [90]. Similar to on-chip processing steps, calculations in the ISP are often manufacturer-specific and can include a variety of operations [6]. Therefore, we will highlight the functionality of some typical ISP components. The most prominent functionality is demosaicing, which converts the captured raw image format (e.g., Bayer pattern) into an RGB image, where each pixel represents three colors instead of individual color components [106]. Since this spatial operation can introduce artifacts, various demosaicing methods, and subsequent correction techniques are available [125]. Additionally, the bit depth per pixel is typically reduced, as the raw data from the image sensor often has a high bit depth [95]. On the RGB image, many further image quality-enhancing processing steps can be performed, such as color or tone correction [14] or extended image denoising [8]. Lastly, ISPs can perform image scaling and/or cropping steps to prepare the captured image data for the subsequent application [146]. Additionally, full-size or scaled images can often be lossy compressed by the ISP [106]. The prepared image is often used by the application layer to update image sensor settings such as the exposure control or camera gains [149]. Sophisticated image sensors have such functionality already on-chip [123].

Application Layer: The final layer of the image processing pipeline includes various applications for different tasks. For autonomous vehicles, CV algorithms are the most important. Among these, ML models are the most common for fully autonomous

vehicles. These models can range from simple object detection algorithms to complex systems, such as trajectory planning based on images or even end-to-end autonomous driving models [20]. Other applications include the fusion of image data with other sensor data, such as LiDAR, the visualization of images in the vehicle’s infotainment system, and many others. In addition, this layer includes applications that control the parameters of preceding components. Examples include configuring the ISP or adjusting sensor settings to influence exposure control. This feedback loop is depicted in Figure 2 as a control flow from the application layer to the ISP and the image sensor. Similar to the data preparation layer, sophisticated image sensors might have application layer functionality already on-chip [122].

3 Security Classification

After introducing the image processing pipeline, we now analyze the security research related to the various layers. We reviewed 56 security-related research papers with the methodology for their selection detailed in Appendix A. From this analysis, we define **eight attack classes** to classify the different types of attacks discussed in these papers. Additionally we categorize them into three groups: (i) Attack Papers \odot : Papers that present an attack against one or more of the pipeline components. This category includes papers that mention possible defenses for the discussed attack but without thorough evaluation \ominus ; (ii) Attack and Defense Papers \bullet : Papers that propose an attack and also include respective defense methods with evaluation, or (iii) Defense Papers \ominus : Papers that focus solely on defense methods. We then map each security-related work to the corresponding layer of the image processing pipeline and highlight the respective vulnerable asset in Table 1.

3.1 Physical World

In the physical world, attacks are separated into three classes: ① *Dynamic Physical Adversarial Distortions*, ② *Static Physical Adversarial Distortions*, and ③ *Targeted Light Attacks*. Additionally, it contains \textcircled{D} *Defenses*. Many existing surveys summarize the research on these physical adversarial samples [4, 45, 134, 136, 140, 141]. We emphasize that more sophisticated physical attacks, exploiting sensor characteristics [82] are covered separately in §3.2.

① **Dynamic Physical Adversarial Distortions:** Attackers can project [41, 78, 93] or display images [99] on physical layer items to disrupt the functionality of cameras in autonomous vehicles. While [41, 99] solely show attacks, [78, 93] propose additional mitigation strategies via adversarial training [78] or improved ML models [93]. All these attacks can be adapted dynamically to change, for example, the size or the content of the adversarial distortions. While this typically increases the attack complexity, it can compensate for changing environmental conditions or viewing angles.

② **Static Physical Adversarial Distortions:** By using printed images [34, 54, 57, 60, 69, 135], stickers [34, 49, 61, 161], or even three dimensional objects [7, 105], attackers can create persistent attacks in the physical world. Typically, environmental influences must be considered when creating such static distortions [57, 60, 69, 161]. Additionally, such perturbations could be overlays on complete objects [54, 135] or stickers only on a small region [34]. While most

work [7, 34, 49, 57, 60, 69, 105, 135] provide attacks, some also provide mitigations [89, 161]. Unlike ① dynamic physical adversarial distortions, static ones remain fixed and cannot be changed during deployment since they need to be recreated or newly placed.

③ **Targeted Light Attacks:** With targeted light, attackers can either directly blind cameras [100] and saturate the resulting image or use reflections from natural [52, 133] or artificial light sources [11, 31]. In most cases, laser pointers, creating a strong light beam, are typical attack devices [11, 31, 100]. These non-persistent attacks can also be found in other application domains of cameras [38, 130].

\textcircled{D} **Defenses:** Feng et al. [36] introduce static physical adversarial distortions that can be used to detect and defend against malicious physical adversarial distortions.

3.2 Sensor Layer

The sensor layer is critical because it is the first point where researchers and engineers can actively influence system design, offering opportunities not only for attacks but also for defending the image processing pipeline. There is a variety of available attack classes: ① *Dynamic Physical Adversarial Distortions*, ③ *Targeted Light Attacks*, ④ *Invasive Environmental Influences*, ⑤ *Image Processing Attacks*, ⑥ *Rolling Shutter Attacks*, and a \textcircled{D} *Defense*.

① **Dynamic Physical Adversarial Distortions:** By using projectors, attackers can exploit lens flare effects, causing optical artifacts due to reflections [82]. Another attack, presented by Xia and Chen [145], exploits the array structure of photosensitive elements in image sensors when showing images on a display. They demonstrate that the Moiré effect, typically seen when geometric patterns such as lines intersect at certain angles [97], can occur on image sensors, adversely affecting object classification.

③ **Targeted Light Attacks:** Controlled targeted light can be used to exploit specific characteristics of image sensors, such as their sensitivity to infrared light [114, 137] or specific lenses [163]. Although these attacks are comparable to ③ targeted light attacks in the physical world, they have sensor dependencies and are therefore categorized in the sensor layer.

④ **Invasive Environmental Influences:** In contrast to the previous attacks, invasive environmental influences aim to attack side-channels of image sensors by introducing acoustic [59, 76] or electromagnetic interference [67]. However, these attacks show limitations in their applicability: While electromagnetic interference works only on CCD-based image sensors [67], existing acoustic attacks [59, 76] work only on cameras with movable lens systems.

⑤ **Image Processing Attacks:** Oyama et al. [98] explore an attack targeting the physical connection between the camera and its subsequent device, injecting manipulated image data. It is placed at the boundary between the sensor and data preparation layer.

⑥ **Rolling Shutter Attacks:** As CMOS-based image sensors are the most common image sensor technology in autonomous vehicles, their rolling shutter effect represents a significant vulnerability. Rolling shutter attacks [35, 46, 117, 153] represent illumination-based attacks, working with pulsed light at a high frequency. Similar attacks [21, 53, 71] can also disturb face detection functionality that

Table 2: Evaluation of attacks sorted by layer and evaluated risk. Category details are available in Appendix B.

Layer	Work	Entry Point	Impact S	Impact O	Accuracy	Impact	Knowledge	Equipment	WoO	Expertise	Feasibility	Risk
Physical	[99]	Physical World						Multiple Bespoke	< 100m			1
	[7]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			1
	[61]	Physical World						Multiple Bespoke	< 100m			1
	[49]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			1
	[161]	Physical World						Specialized	< 100m			2
	[34]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			2
	[54]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			2
	[105]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			2
	[57]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			3
	[133]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			3
	[69]	Physical World						Specialized	< 100m			3
	[135]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			4
	[60]	Physical World						Specialized	< 100m			4
	[100]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			4
	[31]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			4
	[52]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			4
	[89]	Physical World						Multiple Bespoke	< 100m			4
[41]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			5	
[78]	Physical World						Specialized	< 100m			5	
[11]	Physical World						Specialized	< 100m			5	
[93]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			5	
Sensor	[59]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 0.1m			1
	[76]	Physical World						Specialized	< 0.1m			1
	[98]	Sensor / Data						Multiple Bespoke	< 0.1m			1
	[71]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 1m			2
	[163]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			3
	[53]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			3
	[21]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			3
	[82]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			3
	[67]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 1m			3
	[114]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 100m			4
	[117]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 0.5m			4
	[153]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			4
	[68]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			4
	[35]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			4
	[46]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			5
[145]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			5	
[137]	Physical World						Specialized	< 10m			5	
Data Pr.	[103]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			3
	[73]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			3
	[72]	Application Layer						Standard	remote			3
	[146]	Application Layer						Standard	remote			3
Application	[148]	Application Layer						Standard	remote			1
	[80]	Application Layer						Standard	remote			1
	[92]	Physical World						Standard	< 10m			2
	[115]	Physical World						Bespoke	< 10m			3
	[15]	Physical World						Specialized	< 1m			4
	[2]	Application Layer						Standard	remote			4

Accuracy: Targeted, Untargeted
 Impact: Negligible, Moderate, Major, Severe
 Knowledge: white-box, gray-box, black-box
 Feasibility: Very Low, Low, Medium, High
 Expertise: Layman, Proficient, Expert, Multiple Experts
 Risk: According to ISO 21434 [56] from low to high

4 Risk & Threat Model Classification

Current security research on camera pipelines often lacks a consistent risk evaluation, resulting in incomparable or even misleading threat assessments. To address this gap, we systematically evaluate the risk of 48 attack papers (with 8 out of the 56 surveyed papers focusing solely on defense) mapped to the different layers of the pipeline. We assess their impact and feasibility using ISO 21434 [56], a well-defined, internationally recognized industry standard specifically designed to address cybersecurity risks in the automotive industry, ensuring a comprehensive and industry-relevant analysis. Details on the threat analysis and risk assessment with ISO 21434 are given in Appendix B. Table 2 presents the attack impact and feasibility rating as well as the final risk level from low **1** to high **5**. To assess the risk, we include the following categories as defined in ISO 21434 [56]:

- *Asset Identification*: Characterize the layer of the image processing pipeline where the attack unfolds its potential.
- *Attack Path Analysis*: Define the attack entry point used by the attacker.
- *Impact Rating*: Rate the impact ().
- *Attack Feasibility*: Evaluate the feasibility of the attack (Multiple Experts)

All ratings in Table 2 are generated with our interactive tool TARA-CAM³. For each attack, we provide the exact ISO 21434 parameters to enable full reproducibility. Readers can add new attacks or modify any parameter and instantly see the recalculated risk level, enabling exploration of how changes – such as shifting the window of opportunity – affect feasibility.

4.1 Physical World

All physical-world attacks share a common criterion: their entry point is rooted in the physical environment. However, the risk levels of these attacks can vary widely, from low (**1**) to high (**5**). Although most attacks have a severe () and the possibility of them

being targeted () should guide future defensive research of the image processing pipeline.

4.2 Sensor Layer

Similar to the previous layer, nearly all attacks on the sensor layer have their entry point in the physical world, except for [98], which targets the interconnection between the sensor layer and the data preparation layer. Additionally, the risk levels are also distributed from low (**1**) to high (**5**). In contrast to the physical world, attacks with a very low feasibility () but still range up to risk level **3**.

4.3 Data Preparation Layer

While attacks on preceding layers had their attack entry point mainly in the physical world, here we identified the first attacks with an entry point on the application layer [72, 146]. Due to their similar operation principle, all attacks in this layer share a major impact (). These properties lead to a common risk level of **3**.

4.4 Application Layer

Many attacks targeting the application layer [2, 80, 148] also use it as their entry point, setting them apart from most attacks in other layers. A key limitation of these attacks is that the manipulated images must be accessible, often requiring stepping-stone attacks through other components, which adds complexity. However, exceptions exist, such as those described in [115] and [15], which target the application layer while using the physical world as entry points. Irrespective of the entry point, the impact of all attacks ranges from moderate (), the highest risk level of these attacks is **4**.

Observation 3: Attacks on the physical world and sensor layers often combine high feasibility, little system knowledge, and high impact, often resulting in high risk scores. In contrast, attacks in the data preparation and application layers require high expertise and are harder to execute due to possible prior stepping-stone attacks. Yet, some still score high risk due to their high impact. This cross-layer pattern, where knowledge requirements shift from low to high as one moves up the pipeline, emerges clearly only when threats are mapped systematically.

5 Robustness Classification

The development of camera-based autonomous driving solutions has demonstrated a mature level of safe and robust perception, utilizing CV algorithms even in high-speed scenarios for nearly four decades [28]. This progress motivates us to analyze research on the image processing pipeline not only from a security perspective

³<https://tum-esi.github.io/PICT/>

but also by exploring how security can be enhanced through insights from the robustness domain. To achieve this, we reviewed 36 robustness-related studies, with the methodology for selecting and excluding these papers detailed in Appendix A. We map these papers across different layers of the image processing pipeline using multiple criteria and introduce **six robustness classes** that can be used to categorize the collected research papers. By doing so, we aim to bridge the gap between work in the robustness domain and security-related studies, as discussed in §6. The result of the classification of 36 papers is presented in Table 3. The criteria used for classifying the papers include:

- *Layer*: We use the layers of the image processing pipeline in Figure 2 to organize the individual subsections. As many papers operate on multiple layers, we also have subsections on these combined ones.
- *Contribution*: While some work analyzes and optimizes the existing image processing pipeline components, others aim to identify new structures or working principles. We, therefore, differentiate between *Analysis* (Q), analyzing the existing system, *Optimization* (P), aiming to optimize the existing system, and *Upgrades* (S), describing work that aims to use new approaches to increase the robustness.
- *Impact*: Since the human visual perception primarily drove the development of camera systems, we differentiate work that optimizes the *Quality* of images or work that focuses on CV applications, aiming to improve their *Safety*. There is also research considering both categories.
- *Effort*: This represents the effort that is necessary to implement the proposed work in a system. It can be: (i) a *minor software* update (□); (ii) a *major software* update (■); (iii) a necessary *hardware* upgrade (■), or (iv) changes that even concern the surrounding *infrastructure* (■).

5.1 Physical World / Sensor Layer

I Environmental and Data Processing Analysis: In general, work that acts both in the physical world and in the sensor layer can be allocated to this class, where some work analyzes the effect of environmental influences and sensor distortions [18, 51], or even provide datasets for evaluation [128], and other work explains on a more theoretical level the performance of CV algorithms under the influence of random changes [48, 58]. In a different analysis, Bijelic et al. [13] investigate environmental effects on both standard CMOS cameras and so-called gated cameras. This supporting work on more robust CV algorithms can also increase the robustness against adversarial distortions both in the real world and in the application layer.

5.2 Sensor Layer

In contrast to the previous subsection, here we focus exclusively on research related to the sensor layer. We identified three defense classes: **II Anti-Flicker Improvements**, **III CFA Improvements**, and **IV Low-Layer Sensor Improvements**.

II Anti-Flicker Improvements: Various methods exist to detect and mitigate the flickering effect of pulsed Light-Emitting

Diodes (LEDs) [10, 26, 118]. Many automotive image sensors already support LED flicker mitigation, often using proprietary algorithms [96]. Since these algorithms are often integrated directly on the chip, they typically require a high implementation effort, although it is also possible to implement such functions as part of the data preparation in a separate component [9].

III CFA Improvements: This class focuses on improvements of the CFA for automotive-specific requirements, which can influence the outcome of attacks that use digital images or targeted light. Research has examined CFAs tailored to the automotive industry [19, 39, 142]. While [142] and [39] explore the best existing CFA for traffic signal detection, Chakrabarti [19] proposes replacing the traditional Bayer CFA with an adaptive learned CFA.

IV Low-Layer Sensor Improvements: A multitude of improvements of the image sensor is available. These improvements can include advanced lens stacks, which are crucial for creating high-quality images and can significantly boost the performance of object detection algorithms [24]. Additionally, HDR image sensors can play a vital role in defending against simple blinding attacks through targeted light by sequentially capturing multiple images with varying exposure settings to create a single image with a higher dynamic range [84]. Although potentially introducing motion artifacts on fast-moving objects, image sensors with such an HDR feature onboard are common in the automotive industry [113]. Another area of low-layer sensor improvements aims to reduce the rolling shutter effect, which is particularly important in high-speed scenarios [121, 132]. Furthermore, sensor hardware properties can be leveraged to generate more realistic noise in artificial images [12], which can be utilized in technologies such as training data randomization [147] or adversarial training [81]. While much of the research is focused on optimizing image quality for the human visual system, some studies also enhance the performance of CV algorithms [10, 12, 24, 118]. Since optimizations and upgrades to the sensor layer often involve hardware changes or even infrastructural modifications, the effort for work in this layer is typically high.

Observation 4: Although robustness-related improvements in the sensor layer can enhance the security of the image processing pipeline, they often come with a high effort, affecting not only the hardware itself but also its infrastructure. This makes a thorough evaluation from a security perspective difficult and shows the need for a camera testbed featuring realistic automotive features.

5.3 Sensor Layer / Data Preparation Layer

Two classes were identified: **I Environmental and Data Processing Analysis**, and **V Digital Image Processing Improvements**.

I Environmental and Data Processing Analysis: Different research focused on analyzing various distortions within the image processing and their impact on neural networks [30, 63] and perception algorithms [101]. The analyzed distortions relate to digital images, printed objects, or adversarial distortions from security-related research.

V Digital Image Processing Improvements: Improvements in this class aim to ameliorate digitized image data processing. Since

Table 4: Comparing security- and robustness-related research work. Many works act on similar operational principles. As highlighted by the green references, some attack classes received additional research from defensive security work.

	Layer		Physical			Sensor					Data Prep.	App.		
	Class	Security	①	②	③	①	③	④	⑤	⑥	⑤	⑦	⑧	
	Robustness	Work	[99] [41] [93] [78]	[7] [34] [105] [57] [69] [135] [54] [49] [61] [60] [161] [89]	[100] [11] [31] [52] [133]	[145] [82]	[163] [114] [137]	[59] [67] [76]	[98]	[53] [21] [117] [46] [71] [153] [68] [35]	[103] [72] [73] [146]	[2]	[148] [15] [115]	[80] [92]
Physical/ Sensor	I	[18] [13] [51] [128] [48] [58]	✓ [36]	✓ [36]	✓			✓					✓	
Sensor	I	[12]				✓								
	II	[26] [10] [118]								✓				
	III	[39] [142] [19]	✓				✓							
	IV	[24] [84] [132] [121]	✓		✓					✓				
Sensor/ Data Prep.	I	[63] [30]	✓	✓	✓								✓	
	V	[150] [101] [14] [149] [91] [90] [111] [138] [50] [65] [27] [154] [151] [16]	✓	✓	✓			✓	[87]		✓ [104] [87]	[87]	[87]	
Data Prep.	I	[5]	[160]	[160]	[160]							✓	[160]	
App.	VI	[77] [164]	✓ [47, 79, 83]	✓ [47, 79, 83]	[47, 157]		[157]						✓ [47, 79, 83]	

a robustness perspective. Additionally, well-known robustness measures, such as light flicker mitigation technologies (II), can help mitigate rolling-shutter attacks (⑥) that exploit the sensor sensitivity to fast flickering light. Such close relations show that the whole image processing pipeline must be considered when crafting both attacks and defenses on camera systems. Another observation is the distribution of the work among the layers: The data preparation layer received significantly more robustness-related research, while the security research showed more available work in the physical world. By contrast, highly specialized, recent timing attacks [80, 92] neither have directly related countermeasures nor show strong similarities to existing robustness-related research.

The consideration of robustness-related research and the complete image processing pipeline is necessary, since existing security industry standards [87] can protect only a fraction of possible attacks. Especially attacks that originate in the physical world (①, ②, and ③), or attacks that exploit specific sensor characteristics (④, and ⑥) are still possible with state-of-the-art security measures of industry standards.

Observation 5: Robustness research on the image processing pipeline is unevenly distributed: many works concentrate on the sensor and data preparation layers, often with high-effort hardware upgrades, while the physical world and application layers see less direct attention. Certain approaches, particularly environmental and processing analyses, appear in multiple layers, reflecting their potential to thwart attacks across the pipeline.

7 Image Processing Pipeline Testbed

To leverage the insights from our SoK, we built PICT, an image processing pipeline testbed designed for academic experimentation.

PICT is not intended to replicate the full complexity of commercial multi-camera stacks, but to embody the complexity and extensive configuration options of the image processing pipeline identified as missing in existing tools. It allows for manipulating image processing pipeline parameters and investigating intermediate images, contributing to both security research from Table 1 and robustness research of camera systems from Table 3. Moreover, it facilitates developing and testing attacks and countermeasures on the image processing pipeline by enabling controlled image capture with defined settings. Despite the significant demand for such a platform, to our knowledge, no open testbed simultaneously offers realistic hardware, comprehensive pipeline-layer coverage, and reproducibility.

Many existing studies, such as [2, 7, 18, 19, 22, 24, 30, 47, 73, 148], have conducted evaluations without fully utilizing hardware testbeds, relying instead on existing datasets or simulations [14, 15, 80, 99, 105]. On the other hand, real-world evaluations involving hardware testbeds often use one of two types of image-capturing devices: (i) *Smartphone cameras* [17, 21, 34, 35, 57, 59, 68, 71, 76, 117, 153, 160, 161], or (ii) *(Semi-) Professional cameras* [12, 27, 41, 72, 90, 128, 154, 160]. Finally, existing testbeds for interacting with image processing pipeline layers do not represent state-of-the-art technology [1, 112]. These observations motivate the development of PICT, a testbed with embedded hardware and software for evaluating multiple pipeline parameters.

Design Considerations: Based on the limitations of existing solutions, we outline key design considerations of PICT:

- (1) *Representative image sensor:* It should feature realistic sensor sizes, as these impact image quality. For example, the iPhone 8 Plus as used in [17] has a sensor size of 32.3 mm² [25], whereas the EOS Rebel T6i, used in [41], has a much larger sensor of 332.3 mm² [29]. As a reference, automotive sensors

are typically smaller with a sensor size of $\approx 25 \text{ mm}^2$ [95, 96, 113]. Lastly, it should cover a wide field of view of $\geq 100^\circ$, similar to real automotive cameras [23, 88, 110, 131, 155].

- (2) *Use case consideration*: PICT should be able to configure settings that align with automotive CV algorithms rather than visually appealing images. Features like advanced lens systems, including optical zoom, which are uncommon or unavailable in automotive systems, should not be considered.
- (3) *Modularity and hardware access*: PICT should allow for low-level access to sensor interconnections, which is often restricted in fully assembled devices. This enables the usage of alternative image sensors for specific requirements.
- (4) *Consideration of all layers*: PICT must encompass all layers of the image processing pipeline, as depicted in Figure 2. Current testbeds often overlook lower layers, such as the sensor layer [64].

Hardware Architecture: PICT uses a *Camera Module 3 Wide* with a Sony IMX708 image sensor for evaluation and development with max. 11.9MP and a 102° field of view [107]. This camera module supports real-world automotive features, such as an HDR mode, and many settings that can be controlled manually. We use a *Raspberry Pi* as an embedded device with the MIPI-CSI-2 camera interface that is also used in automotive systems on chip [109]. The Raspberry Pi is solely selected for its ability to provide an easily configurable environment that aligns with the purpose of the testbed, making it an appropriate choice for our investigation. It is not part of the performance characteristics of the image processing pipeline. With a hardware investment of $\approx \$70$, this enables researchers to cost-effectively analyze the image processing pipeline. At the same time, the use of standardized interfaces and easily available hardware components allows modifications, such as adding other sensors.

Software Architecture: To capture and evaluate images, we offer three software tools that enable interaction with different modules of the image processing pipeline. The modular design and standardized data formats facilitate integration with other tools:

- (1) *Image Capturing*: Allows the capturing of images both before and after the ISP, including the configuration of the on-chip processing and the ISP parameters. Since the camera module transmits only one image to the Raspberry Pi, both images can be compared since there is no delay or second exposure.
- (2) *Low-Level Analysis*: Enables a manual inspection and analysis of two captured images. It allows researchers to investigate the effect of parameter changes on the captured image. Besides visual inspection, it calculates statistical metrics.
- (3) *Application-specific Analysis*: We provide a Faster R-CNN-based object detection tool as an example software [108]. By reading both the pre-ISP and post-ISP image files, PICT allows for the analysis of how individual parameters impact object detection. Additionally, PICT supports custom tools due to the use of standardized data formats.

8 Evaluation

We will demonstrate the usability and benefits of PICT as well as the influence of the holistic consideration of the image processing pipeline by: (i) showcasing PICT’s ability to test proposed defense

Figure 3: Defensive analysis: blinding attack and HDR imaging as a possible mitigation for the region of interest.

Figure 4: Histogram of the difference of Figures 3b and 3c.

mechanisms of Table 4; (ii) providing a better understanding of attacks through analysis capabilities and supporting a more accurate realization of attack scenarios \llcorner , and (iii) highlighting PICT’s impact by comparing its result with unrealistic mobile phone cameras, commonly used in research. We selected representative attacks of different classes, but other attacks can be evaluated similarly.

8.1 Defensive Use Case Analysis

We use PICT to evaluate HDR imaging [84, 143] as a mitigation for camera blinding attacks [100], an example of the overlooked robustness–security connections discussed in §6. While camera blinding poses a significant risk, our test shows that HDR functionality reduces the effect of highly saturated regions in the image.

For our test, we placed a real stop sign 10 meters away from our testbed and positioned the laser of a commercially available laser rangefinder (Leica Disto A5) directly below the stop sign, aimed straight into the camera. The benign reference image is shown in Figure 3a. The correct stop sign goes undetected when the camera is blinded and HDR is inactive. Figure 4 shows the histogram of the difference between Figure 3b (without HDR) and Figure 3c (with HDR) of the post-ISP image as one possibility to compare the images with the low-level analysis tool. While the red color channel shows a high amount of equal pixel values, representing the saturated pixels of the laser beam, there is a local maximum at an image difference of approx. 25 DN. By contrast, the green and blue channels show a maximum difference at a negative value. This means that the non-HDR image (Figure 3b) shows a more intense red color in the analyzed region, while green and blue are stronger in the HDR image (Figure 3c). This stronger color differentiation can explain why the stop sign is detected in the HDR image. The further the maxima of the individual color components drift apart, the higher the impact of the HDR since the color components will be strongly separated.

Figure 5: Attack use case analysis: Physical adversarial sample compared to digital representation and improved digital representation for the region of interest.

Figure 6: Histograms for the upper stickers in Figure 5.

8.2 Attack Use Case Analysis

In another use case analysis, we use PICT to demonstrate how low-level pipeline analysis can bridge the gap between digitally designed attacks and their physical-world counterparts. For this test, we use adversarial patches of [120], a variant of [34], which applies an adversarial patch to a stop sign to evade detection by the YOLO object detector. We select this use case since some attacks [31, 34] provide a digital simulation of the physical stickers to create and optimize the adversarial patch. In the first step, we capture a real-world stop sign with the applied printed sticker as shown in Figure 5a. We use this image to replace the printed sticker with a digital overlay, depicted in Figure 5b. By performing a low-level analysis, we can see the impact of the overall image processing pipeline and iteratively improve the digital sticker to represent the printed one more accurately in Figure 5c.

Although the real-world hiding attack leads to a low confidence of 0.48 in Figure 5a, the original digital sticker results in a more successful hiding attack in Figure 5b. Figure 6 shows in the upper plot that the histograms of the physical and digital representation of the sticker deviate significantly. By adjusting the brightness of the digital sticker based on the low-level analysis, we can reach a confidence of 0.47 for the improved digital sticker, which is close to the confidence of the physical sticker. As shown in the lower plot of Figure 6, the intensity follows the physical sticker closer.

8.3 Processing Pipeline Use Case Analysis

As previously shown, many attacks were evaluated using mobile phone cameras [17, 21, 34, 35, 57, 59, 68, 71, 76, 117, 153, 160, 161]. While convenient, they have image sensors, optics, and ISP configurations that differ significantly from automotive cameras, leading to attack evaluations that may not transfer to real systems. We use

(a) PICT, classified as a "traffic sign." (b) iPhone, classified as a "moving van."

Figure 7: Impact analysis: While the patched stop sign from the iPhone is repeatedly misclassified, images captured with PICT are correctly classified by Inception v3.

PICT to compare the effect of adversarial RP_2 patches [34] when captured with an automotive-like camera and a mobile phone. For our test, we use an iPhone SE 2020 [43], with a comparable camera as in the original work [34, 42, 44]. We craft the stickers to perform a targeted attack against the Inception v3 classifier model [126] to misclassify a "traffic sign" into a "spindle," an arbitrarily chosen target class. As shown in Figure 7, we captured ten images of the adversarially patched stop sign with PICT and an iPhone SE 2020. Although both image sensors capture images with ≈ 12 MP, iPhone images from Figure 7b are constantly misclassified with an average confidence of 0.40. By contrast, PICT images from Figure 7a are only misclassified in three out of ten images with an average confidence of 0.18. We repeated the measurements in a darker environment, confirming these results: All captured iPhone images are misclassified, while images captured with PICT are not. This use case analysis shows that different cameras with different configurations can yield significantly different attack results, despite capturing images under identical environmental conditions.

9 Conclusion

In this SoK, we investigated security-related research on all layers of the image processing pipeline. We classified the attacks on this pipeline by adapting the automotive security standard ISO 21434. Additionally, we surveyed robustness-related research on the pipeline and identified six main classes of work. By analyzing both security- and robustness-related research, we aimed to take a first step towards closing the existing research gap between these domains and identified the need for a testing environment. With our proposed testbed PICT, we enable researchers to modify several components on all layers of the pipeline and analyze the system impact of individual component changes, allowing further research on security and robustness. Three use case analyses show the benefit of our testbed and highlight that the two research domains must be considered in unison. Future work on the five identified research gaps can help make the overall system more secure and robust.

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A Research Methodology

As a literature basis for this SoK, we searched in common search engines, such as "Google Scholar" for scientific literature published in the security and robustness domains of the image processing pipeline, following the snowballing system [144]. For both domains, we consider work irrespective of its publication date but limited our search to research that applies to autonomous vehicles, as this is a given constraint of our SoK.

As part of the security-related work, we included the work based on the following criteria:

- The work exploits working principles of (parts of) the image processing pipeline of Figure 2.
- The work represents a pure attack, an attack with proposed mitigation, or a pure defense concept.

Similarly, for the robustness-related work, we included it based on the following criteria:

- The work improves and/or analyzes (parts of) components in the image processing pipeline concerning both image quality and more robust CV applications.
- The work represents either an analysis of the existing system or provides improvements on the robustness.

We explicitly exclude the following research:

- Work that shows more generic physical adversarial samples. We refer to existing surveys for interested readers [45, 134, 136, 140, 141].
- Work that works on more abstract levels for both attacks [4, 124, 127] and defenses [81, 147].
- Work that focuses on improving machine learning models irrespective of autonomous vehicles or irrespective of the image processing pipeline. For interested readers, we refer to existing surveys [75, 159, 162].

B Risk Analysis of Camera Attacks

To evaluate the risk of the analyzed attacks on the image processing pipeline of Table 1, we used the steps given by the "Threat analysis and risk assessment methods" in ISO/SAE 21434:2021(E) [56]. Here, we want to provide additional insights into the available categories and the necessary steps to evaluate the risk.

B.1 Asset Identification

In the first step, the asset must be identified. Since we analyze existing attacks on the image processing pipeline depicted in Figure 2, we use the specified layers and the linked work as the asset identification. If further details, such as the exact component, are required, we refer to Table 1, where we specify the affected component. This asset identification only represents the affected component and is not required to calculate the risk.

B.2 Threat Scenario Identification

Since we reference existing research on attacks, the respective linked work gives the threat scenario identification. We do not consider the threat scenario identification separately, but we classify the existing attacks into eight classes, as shown in Table 1.

Table 5: Criteria for impact rating based on ISO 21434 [56].

Rating	Safety Impact	Operational Impact
Severe ■■■	Life-threatening or fatal injuries	Loss or impairment of core vehicle function
Major ■■■	Severe and life-threatening injuries	Loss or impairment of important vehicle function
Moderate ■■■	Light or moderate injuries	Partial degradation of vehicle function
Negligible ■■■	No injuries	No or non-perceivable impairment

B.3 Impact Rating

The impact of the attack must be linked to an impact category, which can be severe (■■■), major (■■■), moderate (■■■), or negligible (■■■). The standard recommends using four criteria resulting in the impact category: Impact rating on safety damage, financial damage, operational damage, and privacy damage. Each category can have the same criteria as mentioned before. Since the standard explicitly excludes the specification of weightings of each impact category, we considered only the impact rating on safety damage and operational damage since they have the most drastic impact on the safety of the people and the driving experience. Table 5 shows the safety and operational impact criteria. Additionally, the standard gives the freedom to add additional impact categories. We added the impact category "Accuracy," specifying the targeted accuracy of the attack, with targeted attacks rated as having a higher impact.

B.4 Attack Path Analysis

Similar to asset identification, the existing research work provides attack path analysis. To provide more details on the attack path, we specify the attack entry point in Table 2, which can be different from the layer where the attack is actually effective. The attack path analysis provides additional information on the attack.

B.5 Attack Feasibility Rating

To rate the feasibility of the attack, four ratings are specified in the standard: High (●), Medium (●), Low (●) and Very low (●). Three different methods are proposed to rate the feasibility of which we selected the attack potential-based approach. This approach specifies five core parameters:

- (1) *Elapsed time*: Time to identify a vulnerability, develop and apply a mitigation. Since most attacks exploit hardware characteristics, distorting the actual meaning of this parameter, we excluded it from the calculation.
- (2) *Specialist expertise*: Capability necessary by the attack to perform a successful attack. As shown in Table 6a, it can be Layman (♂), Proficient (♂), Expert (♂) or Multiple Experts (♂♂).
- (3) *Knowledge*: Required knowledge of the item or component. In the given research work, the knowledge can be derived from the assumed threat model, which can be either white-box (□), gray-box (■) or black-box (■) as depicted in Table 6b.
- (4) *Window of Opportunity*: Description of the access conditions to successfully perform an attack. In contrast to the standard, we use the distance of the attack that was evaluated in the

Table 6: Core parameters for attack feasibility rating.

(a) Specialist Expertise			(b) Knowledge		
Enumerate	Symbol	Value	Enumerate	Symbol	Value
Layman	♂	0	Black-box	■	0
Proficient	♂	3	Gray-box	■	5
Expert	♂	6	White-box	□	11
Multiple Experts	♂♂	8			

(c) Window of Opportunity

Enumerate	ISO terminology	Value
< 100m	Unlimited	0
< 10m	Easy	1
< 1m	Moderate	4
< 0.5m	Moderate	4
< 0.1m	Difficult / None	10
Remote	Difficult / None	10

(d) Equipment

Enumerate	Description	Value
Standard	Readily available tools	0
Specialized	Available with moderate effort	4
Bespoke	Specially produced equipment	7
Multiple Bespoke	Various specialized equipment	9

Table 7: Risk matrix based on impact and feasibility.

		Feasibility			
		Very Low ●	Low ●	Medium ●	High ●
Impact	Severe ■■■	1	3	4	5
	Major ■■■	1	2	3	4
	Moderate ■■■	1	1	2	3
	Negligible ■■■	1	1	1	1

original research work. We assign the same numerical values to these categories as given in the standard. An overview is given in Table 6c.

- (5) *Equipment*: Tools (hardware and/or software) required to perform the attack. As shown in Table 6d, it ranges from standard to multiple bespoke.

The overall attack feasibility rating results as a sum of these individual core parameters: 1) High (0 – 13), 2) Medium (14 – 19), 3) Low (20 – 24), and 4) Very Low (25 – 38).

B.6 Risk Value Determination

Based on the impact rating and the attack feasibility rating, the risk value shall be a value between 1 and 5, with 1 representing the lowest risk. The standard does not define a method for how the individual parts are used to calculate the overall risk. It provides two examples, namely risk matrices or risk formulas. We include the rating of impact and feasibility for each attack and calculate the risk value by using the risk matrix of Table 7.